

Artículo de Investigación

The Impact of Body Mass Index on Balance and Fall Risk Among Individuals Aged 40 to 80 Years: A Systematic Review.

El impacto del índice de masa corporal en el equilibrio y el riesgo de caídas entre individuos de 40 a 80 años: Una revisión sistemática.

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RESUMEN

La obesidad, caracterizada por la acumulación excesiva de tejido adiposo, ha mostrado un aumento significativo en su prevalencia desde 1975 hasta 2016. Esta tendencia plantea una creciente preocupación debido a su asociación con un aumento en los riesgos de caídas y lesiones subsiguientes. El Índice de Masa Corporal (IMC) cuantifica el peso corporal de adultos. El exceso de masa corporal afecta adversamente el equilibrio y la marcha, disminuyendo así la calidad de vida entre adultos de mediana y avanzada edad. Este estudio tiene como objetivo evaluar la influencia del IMC en el equilibrio y el riesgo de caídas. Material y Métodos: Esta revisión sistemática utilizó las bases de datos PubMed, Cochrane, MEDLINE y PEDro para la búsqueda de literatura realizada entre enero y febrero de 2020, centrándose en estudios publicados entre 2014 y 2020 que incluyeran individuos de 40 a 80 años. Resultados: Nueve artículos cumplieron con los criterios de inclusión. Se observaron correlaciones significativas entre el IMC y un mayor riesgo de caídas, pérdida de equilibrio, inestabilidad postural y deterioro de la salud en hombres y mujeres obesos. La prevalencia de caídas con lesiones varió según la edad y el género. Conclusión: El IMC ejerce una influencia notable en el equilibrio, contribuyendo a un aumento en los riesgos de caídas, miedo a caer, limitaciones en la actividad física y desafíos en las actividades diarias. Se requiere investigación adicional para dilucidar la dinámica de recuperación de caídas y proporcionar conocimientos sobre los riesgos de caídas entre la población adulta.

Palabras claves: índice de masa corporal; IMC; equilibrio; obesidad; estabilidad.

ABSTRACT

Overweight and obesity, characterized by excessive adipose tissue accumulation, have shown a significant increase in prevalence from 1975 to 2016. This trend poses a growing concern due to its association with elevated risks of falls and subsequent injuries. Body Mass Index (BMI) serves as the primary metric for quantifying adult body weight. Excessive body mass adversely affects balance and gait, thereby diminishing the quality of life among middle-aged and older adults. This study aims to assess the influence of BMI on balance and the risk of falls. Material and Methods: This systematic review utilized PubMed, Cochrane, MEDLINE, and PEDro databases for literature search conducted between January and February 2020, focusing on studies published from 2014 to 2020 involving individuals aged 40 to 80 years and reported in English. Results: Nine articles met the inclusion criteria. Significant correlations were observed between BMI and increased risk of falls, loss of balance, postural instability, and deteriorating health among obese men and women. The prevalence of injurious falls varied by age and gender. Conclusions: BMI exerts a notable influence on balance, contributing to heightened fall risks, fear of falling, physical activity limitations, and challenges in daily living activities. Further research is warranted to elucidate fall recovery dynamics and provide deeper insights into fall risks among the aging population.

Keywords: body mass index; BMI; balance; obesity; stability.

1. Introduction

Overweight and obesity are significant health concerns associated with a range of specific health conditions (1,2). Obesity develops due to an imbalance between energy intake and expenditure, exacerbated by age-related reductions in basal metabolic rate (3,4). Body Mass Index (BMI), calculated as weight (kg) divided by height squared (m^2), serves as a straightforward measure to classify adults as overweight or obese (5-7). A BMI above 30.0 is linked to increased mortality risk (5,8).

The rise in obesity prevalence over the past four decades is primarily driven by environmental and dietary changes rather than genetic factors (9). This trend has visibly altered physical structures and impaired functional abilities in individuals (10-17). Physical inactivity and obesity are major contributors to global mortality (18,19). Obesity also increases the risk of cardiometabolic diseases (20), physical disability (21), reduced quality of life (22), sexual dysfunction (23), lower urinary tract symptoms (24), cognitive decline (25), and dementia (26). Overweight individuals are more susceptible to chronic diseases and associated symptoms that affect their quality of life (27-29), such as hypertension (30-32), diabetes (33), hyperlipidemia (34), cancer (35,36), arthritis (37-39), respiratory disorders (40,41), and urinary incontinence (15,28), among others (39).

Maintaining good balance is essential for daily functioning (40-44), and difficulties in performing activities associated with higher BMI highlight its impact on balance impairment (27). Balance disorders are increasingly recognized as a significant public health concern due to their strong association with falls (19,27). Excessive body mass is known to compromise balance, contributing to a higher incidence of falls and reduced quality of life among middle-aged and older adults (45-48). As obesity-related disabilities continue to rise, there is an urgent need to deepen our understanding of its effects on mobility and balance (49-52). This study aims to investigate the relationship between body mass index and balance impairment and fall risk (50-53).

2. Development

In systematic reviews, the construction of a flow diagram is crucial for transparently illustrating the selection process of studies included in the review. Initially, a comprehensive search across multiple databases yielded a total of 234 articles (Fig. 1). Specifically, 61 articles were identified in PubMed, 52 in Cochrane, 81 in Medline, and 40 in PEDro. Subsequently, a preliminary screening was conducted based on titles containing relevant keywords, resulting in 74 potentially relevant articles. Following this, abstracts of these articles were scrutinized, leading to the exclusion of studies that did not specify participant numbers or the assessment conducted, as well as those that compared balance with irrelevant criteria, thereby reducing the pool to 52 articles. Duplicate studies were then removed, resulting in 48 articles. The remaining articles underwent full-text review, during which studies comparing the keywords with unrelated diseases, those correlating balance with cognitive, vestibular, or neuromuscular disorders, and those lacking categorization of participants by BMI were excluded. Ultimately, after completion of this rigorous analysis, a total of 9 articles met the criteria for inclusion in the present study.

Fig 1. Flow diagram of searched, screened, and included studies.
Prepared by: Juan Pablo Arias Córdova

Boolean operators are fundamental tools in systematic literature searches, enhancing the precision and scope of information retrieval from databases. These operators, namely AND, OR, and NOT, facilitate the construction of complex search queries by linking keywords and

concepts. In the context of this study, Boolean operators were applied to search databases such as Medline Complete, PubMed, Cochrane, and PEDro. For instance, combinations like "body mass index OR bmi AND obesity AND stability" were used in Medline Complete to broaden the search results, whereas PubMed employed "body mass index AND obesity AND stability" to focus on studies meeting all specified criteria. Cochrane utilized "body mass index AND stability AND balance" to target articles relevant to balance and stability, and PEDro applied "body mass index AND balance" to refine results. These operators ensure that only relevant studies within the designated timeframe (2014-2020), involving human subjects aged 40 years and older, and published in English were included.

DATABASES	
Annex strategy	<p>Medline Complete Connectors: body mass index OR BMI AND obesity AND stability Language: English Study Subjects: Humans Age: Adults 40 +years Period: January 2014- February 2020</p>
	<p>PubMed Connectors: body mass index AND obesity AND stability Language: English Study Subjects: Humans Age: Adults 40 +years Publications of the last 5 years</p>
	<p>Cochrane Connectors: body mass index AND stability AND balance. Language: English Period: January 2014- February 2020</p>
	<p>PEDro Connectors: body mass index AND balance. Language: English Period: January 2014- February 2020</p>

1. Search

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In the context of the systematic review conducted on the relationship between body mass index (BMI), balance, obesity, and stability, the use of abbreviations enhances clarity and efficiency in communicating key concepts and findings. The primary abbreviations utilized include BMI (body mass index), QoL (quality of life), RCTs (randomized controlled trials), and OR (odds ratio), among others. These abbreviations are introduced at their first mention in the manuscript, accompanied by their full definitions, to facilitate understanding and streamline the presentation of complex data and results. Consistent use of these abbreviations throughout the review ensures coherence and readability, aligning with academic conventions and journal guidelines for effective scholarly communication. This approach aims to optimize the accessibility and impact of the systematic review's findings on BMI's influence on balance and stability across different populations. The abbreviations used in this review are listed below

Kg	Kilogram
M	Meter
BMI	Body mass index
BRFSS	Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System
DBATS	Dynamic Balancing Ability Test Scale
ML	Mid-lateral
AP	Anterior-posterior
SOT	Sensory Organization Test
LOS	Limits of Stability
CDP	Computed Dynamic Posturography
TUG	Time up and go
RWS	Rhythmic Weight Shift
PASE	Physical Activity Scale for the Elderly
COMv	Velocity of center of mass
COMa	Acceleration of the center of mass
COM	Center of mass
CoP	Center of pressure
MLV	Mid-lateral Velocity
VAP	Velocity anterior-posterior
EO	Eyes open
EC	Eyes closed

In this systematic review, the results have been categorized based on author, study design, sample size, variables, interventions, and outcomes. Each study's authorship is identified to attribute findings accurately. The study designs are classified to distinguish between

observational, experimental, and clinical trial methodologies, ensuring methodological diversity in the analysis. Sample sizes are documented to assess the studies' statistical power and generalizability. Variables under investigation, such as body mass index (BMI), balance measures, and obesity-related factors, are systematically documented for comparative analysis. Interventions applied in intervention studies are outlined to evaluate their impact on balance and stability outcomes. Finally, study results are summarized to provide insights into the associations between BMI, obesity, and balance in older adults, emphasizing variations in findings across different studies and populations.

First author of the publication	Design	Subjects	Variables	Intervention	Results
Ercan, S et al. (2020)	Observational, cross-sectional study	Age: 40-60 251 subjects, 129 (51.4%) women and 122 (48.6%) men. Obese group 125 (49.8%) subjects.	Obesity Gender Balance Posture Risk and fear of falls	Tinetti Test Balance Confidence Scale in Specific Activities Fall History Scale One leg stance test Functional scope test The New York Posture Qualification Test	High activity restriction in obese women for fear of falling. Posture was altered in 125 (100%) obese individuals and all experienced loss of balance. Obese men did not experience fear of falling. Significant negative relationship between BMI, loss of balance and altered posture.
Yitalo, K et al. (2014)	Observational, cross-sectional study	Age: 45 a 79 280,035 adults	Age Sex Obesity Risk of falls Harmful falls	Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System BRFSS Follow-up telephone surveys.	Overweight was associated with harmful falls in middle-aged women. II/III obesity was associated with injurious falls among all age and gender groups.
Gao, X et al. (2019)	Observational, prospective study	Age: 69,5 ± 6,4. 53 subjects	Obesity Risk of falls Dynamic stability Gait	Motion analysis system. Dynamic Balance Ability Test Scale (DBATS).	Obesity can worsen balance. A high BMI decreases the dynamic stability and balance of the elderly.
Traves, C et al. (2018)	Observational, retrospective study	Age: 72.68±7.40 98 subjects	Obesity Risk of falls Postural balance	Comprehensive Geriatric Evaluation Longitudinal Evaluation of Fall History Force Platform Measurement unit fixed on the sternum	Body weight/BMI is an additional risk factor for falls in the elderly and may be a marker for fall risk.
Rezaeiipour, M et al. (2018)	Observational study, cohort	Age: 45 y 65 años. 111 men	Weight Balance postural stability Usual environment	Test standing with eyes open and closed. Center of pressure velocity in ML and AP directions. Force platform for postural stability	Negative influence of obesity on postural stability in the AP direction. In the ML direction obese men were more stable than normal weight men.
Rossi, M et al. (2015)	Observational study, cases and controls	Age: 65+ 135 patients, 104 women and 31 men	Obesity Balance Posture Postural instability	Neurocom Smart Platform, Sensory Organization Test (SOT), Limits of Stability (LOS) Computed Dynamic Posturography, (CDP) Time up and go test (TUG), Rhythmic Weight Shift (RWS) Falls Efficacy Scale-International Questionnaire	Obese patients took longer to perform modified TUG and require more steps. It will also exert lower levels on subjective tests. Obese patients are at increased risk of falls compared to non-obese patients.
Hooker, E et al. (2017)	Observational study, cohort	Age: 65+ 5.834 men	Age BMI Rate of falls Physical performance Comorbidities	Follow-up questionnaire every 4 months Nottingham force platform, 6 meters walking test Physical Activity Scale for the Elderly (PASE)	Obesity was associated with an increased risk of falling from 24% to 92% in men younger than 80 years. Alteration in the test for dynamic balance between the association of BMI and falls.
Neri, S et al. (2019)	Observational study, cohort	Age: 60+ 204 women	Obesity Falls Muscle quality in lower limbs Foot load Postural control	Muscle quality (isokinetic dynamometer and dual energy X-ray) Foot loads (pressure platform) and Postural Balance (force platform).	Obesity was associated with an increased risk of falls. Flat foot was the significant mediator of the relationship between obesity and falls.
Neri, S et al. (2017)	Observational, cross-sectional study	Age: 60-80. 147 women	Risk of falls Fear of falling Body adiposity Postural balance	Dual energy X-ray absorptiometry Force Platform International Fall Efficiency Scale QuickScreen Clinical Falls Risk Assessor	All measures of adiposity were correlated with at least 1 parameter of postural stability and fear of falling. The obese group exhibited a higher fear of falling and had a higher proportion of subjects with a higher risk of falling.

**Table 2. Data extraction from each included study.
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The Caspe Scale is a validated tool utilized in academic research to assess the methodological quality and rigor of articles included in systematic reviews or meta-analyses. Developed to enhance transparency and reliability in evidence synthesis, the Caspe Scale evaluates various aspects of study design, execution, and reporting. Key criteria typically considered include the clarity and appropriateness of research objectives, the adequacy of sample size and participant selection methods, the robustness of data collection procedures, the

appropriateness of statistical analyses employed, and the comprehensiveness of results interpretation. By systematically applying the Caspe Scale, researchers can objectively appraise the strengths and limitations of individual studies, thereby facilitating more informed conclusions and recommendations based on the cumulative evidence synthesized from diverse sources.

Autores	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	Total
1 Ercan, S et al. (2020)	YE S	YE S	11/11									
2 Ylitalo, K et al. (2014)	YE S	YE S	NO	YE S	YE S	YE S	YE S	NO	NO	YE S	YE S	8/11
3 Gao, X et al. (2019)	YE S	YE S	10/11									
4 Frames, C et al (2018)	YE S	NO	YE S	10/11								
5 Rezaeipour, M et al. (2018)	YE S	YE S	YE S	YE S	NO	YE S	YE S	YE S	YE S	NO	YE S	9/11
6 Rossi, M et al. (2016)	YE S	YE S	11/11									
7 Hooker, E et al. (2017)	YE S	YE S	YE S	YE S	NO	YE S	YE S	YE S	NO	YE S	YE S	9/11
8 Neri, S et al. (2019)	YE S	YE S	YE S	NO	YE S	YE S	YE S	YE S	NO	YE S	YE S	9/11
9 Neri, S et al. (2017)	YE S	YE S	YE S	NO	YE S	NO	YE S	YE S	YE S	YE S	YE S	9/11
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Clearly defined theme 2. Recruitment properly 3. Precise result minimizing possible biases 4. Effect of confounding factors 5. Long and complete tracking 6. Study results 7. Accuracy of results 8. Credibility of the results 9. Match other available evidence 10. Application of the results 11. Changes in clinical decision 												

Annex 2. Caspe Scale for Cohorts
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The PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines are a recognized framework designed to enhance the transparency, completeness, and quality of reporting in systematic reviews and meta-analyses. Developed to address

deficiencies in reporting found in earlier reviews, PRISMA outlines a structured approach for authors to follow when preparing their manuscripts. The guidelines encompass a checklist of essential items and a flow diagram that detail the steps taken in the review process, from initial search to final inclusion of studies. By adhering to PRISMA, reviewers ensure that their methodology, results, and conclusions are presented in a clear and standardized manner, promoting reproducibility and facilitating critical appraisal by readers and stakeholders. PRISMA's widespread adoption in academic publishing underscores its role in promoting rigorous and transparent reporting practices, thereby enhancing the reliability and credibility of systematic reviews and meta-analyses in evidence-based research.

PRISMA SCALE		
Nº	SECTION/ITEM	RESULT
TITLE		
1	Title	YES
ABSTRACT		
2	Structured Abstract	YES
INTRODUCTION		
3	Justification	YES
4	Objective	YES
METHODS		
5	Protocol and registration	YES
6	Eligibility Criteria	YES
7	Information Sources	YES
8	Search	YES
9	Selection of Studies	YES
10	Data Collection Process	YES
11	Data List	YES
12	Risk of bias in individual studies	NO
13	Summary Measures	YES
14	Summary of Results	YES
15	Risk of bias between studies	NO
16	Additional Analyzes	YES
RESULTS		
17	Selection of studies	YES
18	Characteristics of the studies	YES
19	Risk of bias in studies	NO
20	Results of individual studies	YES
21	Synthesis of the results	YES
22	Risk of bias between studies	NO
23	Additional analyzes	YES
DISCUSSION		
24	Evidence Summary	YES
25	Limitations	YES
26	Conclusions	YES
FINANCING		
27	Financing	YES
TOTAL		23/27

Annex 3. PRISMA Scale
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3. Material and Methods

Study Design

This study constitutes a systematic review wherein relevant studies were identified through electronic databases including PubMed, Cochrane, MEDLINE, and PEDro. The search for scientific articles was conducted from January 2020 to February 2020, and a second researcher independently replicated the search with identical outcomes.

Inclusion Criteria

Articles were included if they met the following criteria: (a) subjects aged between 40 and 80 years (50); (b) studies employing balance scales and/or pressure or force platforms for assessments; (c) studies incorporating BMI measurements; (d) articles published in English.

Exclusion Criteria

Exclusion criteria encompassed: (a) studies involving subjects with a BMI less than 18.5; (b) articles featuring subjects outside the specified age range; (c) studies involving subjects with knee or hip prostheses, musculoskeletal or neuromuscular disorders, hospitalized individuals, or users of technical aids; (d) studies involving subjects with diseases associated with a high risk of falls, degenerative diseases, vestibular disorders, cognitive impairments, or psychiatric conditions; (e) studies involving subjects with clinical conditions that could exacerbate with physical exertion.

Search Strategy

The search strategy employed keywords: 1. body mass index, 2. BMI, 3. balance, 4. obesity, 5. stability. Various combinations of these keywords, along with Boolean operators (AND, OR), were utilized across different databases: Medline Complete: body mass index OR bmi

AND obesity AND stability. PubMed: body mass index AND obesity AND stability. Cochrane: body mass index AND stability AND balance. PEDro: body mass index AND balance.

The search was confined to studies conducted between 2014 and 2020, involving human participants aged 40 years and older, and articles exclusively in English (see Annex 1).

Selection of Articles

Following the application of filters and refinement of the article search, selection was based on assessment of titles and abstracts. Articles were considered eligible if they provided information on sample size, subject age, and BMI percentage. Duplicate articles were removed, and studies comparing variables unrelated to this review (e.g., nutrition, heart rate, weight loss) were excluded. Selected articles underwent detailed methodology review to identify assessment tools such as scales, tests, or programs used. Studies reporting subjects' fall history over the past six to twelve months and noting health (e.g., depression, cardiovascular disease, anxiety, diabetes, sarcopenia, arthritis) and behavioral (e.g., physical activity, sleep) outcomes were included.

Assessment of Methodological Quality

Methodological quality was assessed using the Caspe scale for cohort studies. Articles scoring 8/11 or higher on this scale were considered for inclusion (see Annex 2). Additionally, the PRISMA scale was employed to verify methodological quality upon completion of the review (see Annex 3).

4. Results

Following the database searches, a total of 234 articles were initially identified (Fig. 1). Specifically, 61 articles were retrieved from PubMed, 52 from Cochrane, 81 from Medline, and 40 from PEDro. Initially, a preliminary screening based on titles related to the study's keywords yielded 74 potentially relevant articles. Subsequently, abstracts were reviewed, excluding articles that did not specify total subject numbers or assessment methods, and those comparing unrelated variables related to balance. This screening reduced the number to 52

articles across the databases. Duplicate articles were then removed, resulting in 48 unique articles for full-text evaluation.

Further analysis of these full-text articles involved excluding studies that compared variables not pertinent to this study or that focused on diseases affecting cognitive, vestibular, or neuromuscular systems. Additionally, studies lacking clear categorization of subjects by BMI were excluded. Ultimately, after thorough examination, a total of 9 articles met all inclusion criteria and were included in this study (Table 1).

The identified articles predominantly consisted of observational studies. Among these, two studies (46, 52) included analyses involving both men and women, while two others (53, 54) focused exclusively on men. Additionally, two studies (3, 31) involved only female populations, and three studies (43, 50, 51) did not specify the gender composition of their subjects.

Various methodologies were employed to assess the impact of BMI on physical health outcomes. These methods included:

Balance Assessment: Several studies utilized different tests and scales to evaluate balance among subjects with varying BMI levels (46, 51-54).

Fall Risk Assessment: Surveys and scales were employed in multiple studies to assess the risk of falls associated with BMI (3, 43, 46, 50, 52, 53).

Force or Pressure Plates: Studies utilized force or pressure plates to measure parameters related to balance and stability in relation to BMI (3, 31, 43, 46, 51, 53, 54).

Other Variables: Additionally, four studies focused exclusively on comprehensive geriatric assessments, physical activity levels, muscle quality, or body adiposity as variables of interest (43, 31, 3, 53).

Several studies incorporated combinations of these methodologies to comprehensively evaluate the effects of BMI on the human body (Table 1).

The studies analyzed in this review highlighted several key findings related to the impact of BMI on various health outcomes, including risk of falls, loss of balance, postural alterations, and general health conditions:

Risk of Falls:

Erkan et al. (2020): Found a significant negative correlation between BMI and loss of balance in obese individuals compared to non-obese counterparts. Measures such as the Tinetti test and balance confidence scale were crucial in determining these outcomes.

Ylitalo et al. (2014): Reported that 27% of adults aged 45 to 79 in the United States experienced at least one fall in the past year, with 11% resulting in injurious falls. The risk of falls and injurious falls was higher in individuals with Class I and Class II/III obesity compared to those of normal weight, with Class II/III obese individuals facing a 35-53% increased risk.

Frames et al. (2018): Suggested that BMI serves as an additional risk factor for falls among older adults, indicating significant variability in fall risk among obese individuals.

Rossi et al. (2015): Found that obese patients experienced falls and fall-related hospital admissions, with no statistical differences by gender or age observed.

Hooker et al. (2017): Reported an increased rate of falls with higher BMI, particularly among older men. Those in obesity classes II and III had nearly double the risk of falling compared to men of normal weight in the same age group.

Neri et al. (2019): Noted a higher proportion of falls among obese individuals compared to non-obese individuals (44% vs. 21%). Factors such as altered body structure and inadequate muscle quality in the lower extremities were implicated in the relationship between obesity and falls.

Neri et al. (2017): Identified a significantly higher risk of falls among older obese participants, with 62% of the obese group categorized at increased risk.

Postural and Balance Disturbances:

Erkan et al. (2020): Found significant postural deterioration and loss of balance in obese individuals. They observed a significant negative correlation between BMI, loss of balance, and postural impairment specifically in men.

Gao et al. (2019): Discovered that the peak values of center of mass velocity (COMv) and center of mass acceleration (COMa) decreased with increasing BMI. Participants with higher BMI showed a more anterior position of the normalized center of mass during take-off, indicating slower normalized COMv and COMa. Their study also revealed that the group with the highest BMI had the lowest scores on the DBATS dynamic balance ability test scale, suggesting weaker dynamic balance ability.

Frames et al. (2018): Observed linear variables of postural analysis using force platforms and suggested that obese individuals who experienced falls exhibited higher standard deviations in time series and larger swing areas and ranges. They noted less persistence in the anterior-posterior time series compared to the mediolateral direction in the center of pressure (CoP).

Rezaeipour et al. (2018): Analyzed CoP velocity on a force platform with eyes open and closed conditions. They found significant differences in mean CoP velocity in both anterior-posterior (AP) and mediolateral (ML) directions among three BMI groups. Obese men swayed significantly faster in the AP direction under both eyes open and closed conditions compared to normal weight men. In the ML direction, obese men exhibited greater stability due to an enlarged base of support in a natural position.

Rossi et al. (2015): Noted that obese patients took longer to perform the modified timed up-and-go test (TUG) and required more steps. In computerized dynamic posturography (CDP), no significant differences were found in the sensory organization test (SOT) or limits of stability (LOS). However, there was a statistically significant difference in anteroposterior directional control of rhythmic weight shift (RWS).

Hooker et al. (2017): Utilizing a force platform, observed that overweight and obese men exhibited 13% to 26% greater leg power and 5% to 6% greater grip strength compared to men with normal BMI. However, men with the highest BMI had a 15% slower walking speed in the 6-meter walk compared to those with normal BMI.

Neri et al. (2019): Used a force platform and foot load data to determine that heavier

individuals generated more force while walking compared to leaner counterparts. Obese participants also had a larger contact area underfoot and a flatter foot shape. Postural control parameters indicated that obese individuals showed higher mean CoP displacement along both anteroposterior and mediolateral axes.

Neri et al. (2017): Found that all measures of adiposity were positively correlated with at least one parameter of postural stability. On a force platform, obese individuals exhibited significantly greater mean CoP displacement along both AP and ML axes during experimental conditions with feet apart. Additionally, mean AP CoP displacement was significantly higher in the feet together/eyes closed condition for obese compared to non-obese participants.

Health Condition:

Ercan et al. (2020): Found significant differences in perceived health status between obese and non-obese individuals. Women reported differences in perceived health status, medication use, and presence of chronic diseases compared to non-obese women. Similarly, significant differences were noted among men in perceived health status, medication use, and reported chronic diseases.

Ylitalo et al. (2014): Reported that nearly 20% of adults experienced depression and 39.4% reported arthritis. A higher proportion of middle-aged and older women reported depression and arthritis compared to men. Middle-aged and older men were more likely to report diabetes, sedentary lifestyle, and smoking. They found that depression, cardiovascular disease, diabetes, arthritis, physical activity, and sleep habits were significantly associated with falls and the risk of injurious falls, with depression showing the strongest association across all BMI categories.

Hooker et al. (2017): Identified a higher prevalence of chronic medical conditions among individuals with higher BMI. They found hypertension rates nearly twice as high and diabetes rates three times more prevalent among men in overweight BMI categories. Medication use was also more frequent in men with higher BMI.

Neri et al. (2017): Did not find significant differences between groups based on age, time since menopause, height, hormone replacement therapy, alcohol use, and smoking status.

These studies underscore the impact of BMI on various chronic health conditions and their association with falls and overall health status. They highlight significant disparities in health outcomes related to BMI, emphasizing the importance of managing weight to mitigate health risks.

5. Discussion

The study aimed to investigate the impact of body mass index (BMI) on balance and fall risk (50-53). It not only identified the effects of BMI on balance but also provided substantial evidence of its broader health implications (31, 34). The rising prevalence of obesity necessitates measures to mitigate associated morbidity and premature mortality (55). Among the public health issues stemming from obesity, falls and their ensuing complications stand out prominently (19, 34). The study revealed a heightened incidence of falls and injurious falls among obese adults, with women consistently reporting higher rates of falls and injuries compared to men across all age groups (29, 31).

Middle-aged women were found to have the highest prevalence of falls (31), underscoring the importance of early fall assessment, a critical period often overlooked in existing research (3-5). Stratification by age and sex is essential to pinpoint when obesity starts affecting balance and exacerbating fall risks (56, 57). Evidence suggests that women face a greater risk of injurious falls than men (29, 31), with studies highlighting biological, psychosocial, and functional changes, particularly during the transition from middle age to elderly (5, 31). The midlife phase appears pivotal in this context due to concurrent shifts in body composition and fat distribution during menopause (58-60).

During midlife, individuals are particularly vulnerable to developing obesity due to changes in reproductive hormones associated with menopause (5, 7). These changes often lead to discordant alterations in fat mass and muscle mass levels, which predispose women to poor physical function and disability (10-12). Older women with obesity tend to have higher lean leg mass but not necessarily greater muscle strength (48). Muscle mass and fat infiltration into muscle are closely linked to body weight, possibly exacerbated by gravitational and inertial forces during movement, which can impair muscle contractile capacity and overall physical performance (61, 62). This distribution of body mass away from the ankle's axis of

rotation may require increased ankle activity to counteract gravitational effects, thereby affecting balance control, gait, and the ability to perform daily activities easily (21-24). Reduced reaction time and lower extremity muscle strength further influence postural adjustments and increase the risk of falls (50-52).

Midlife obesity is predictive of disability in later life and may worsen the severity of other chronic health conditions (63). Studies indicate that midlife obesity correlates with a higher likelihood of fall-related injuries, heightened postural instability, and lower muscle strength (6-8), underscoring obesity's significant role in fall risk (31-33). The exact mechanisms linking obesity to increased fall risk remain unclear (64). Hypothesized mechanisms include excessive force during falls, poor muscle quality among obese individuals, or pathological connections between excess adipose tissue and conditions such as peripheral nerve damage or osteoarthritis (34, 35). Obese individuals may also exhibit reduced ability to initiate recovery mechanisms after losing balance, thereby increasing their susceptibility to injurious falls (50-51).

As individuals age, there is a natural decline in leg muscle strength and impulse control, leading to slower walking speeds. Obese older adults experience additional challenges due to bearing greater weight while walking, which further contributes to their slower pace. This reduced movement control in older adults is primarily attributed to muscle and bone deterioration, impacting dynamic stability. Obese individuals tend to adopt a more conservative balance strategy by positioning their Center of Mass (COM) closer to the fulcrum during gait (43-46).

While specific muscle strength measurements were not uniformly assessed in the studies reviewed, it is well-documented that older adults often exhibit weaker tibialis anterior and vastus lateralis muscles compared to their healthier counterparts (43). Aging is associated with progressive muscle loss, particularly type II muscle fibers, contributing to muscle weakness and increased fat infiltration (25, 31). Additionally, participants in the studies displayed a higher dynamic arch index in their feet, indicative of flat feet, potentially stemming from chronic overload conditions (31). High foot loads associated with obesity can lead to foot pain, which in turn disrupts balance and increases the likelihood of falls (25, 27).

Research by Gao et al. (2019) indicates that the additional weight carried by obese individuals affects joint loading and alters gait patterns (51). This suggests that obese older adults rely more on static support for balance control compared to their non-obese counterparts who use dynamic inertial control (51, 52). Such reliance on static support may compromise dynamic stability in obese individuals (4, 6). Those with weaker balance control often adopt cautious gait strategies, including slower walking speeds and shorter steps, which obese older adults may also employ to mitigate fall risks associated with decreased dynamic stability (59-64).

Observations of large pressure values and extensive contact areas under the feet of obese individuals suggest diminished sensory feedback from plantar mechanoreceptors (43). Alterations in this sensory information contribute to increased postural sway and necessitate greater corrective muscle movements and adjustments (41-43). Continuous overload on plantar mechanoreceptors may hyperactivate them, further compromising postural stability in obese individuals (46).

As body mass increases, the energy and force required to support the Center of Mass (COM) during movement also escalates, imposing a greater biomechanical load on lower extremity joints for maintaining balance during ambulation (43). Consequently, obese older adults often adopt adaptive standing strategies to manage this increased load (44-46). Moreover, changes in body fat distribution, reduced range of motion, and altered weight-bearing patterns further contribute to deteriorated posture among obese individuals (50-54). Evaluations of posture indicate that obesity alters body schema, prompting the development of compensatory mechanisms to accommodate these physical changes (39, 40).

Obesity not only compromises posture but also heightens the fear of movement and falling following balance loss (3), significantly diminishing individuals' quality of life, with heightened fear particularly prevalent among those with severe obesity (4-6). This fear can perpetuate a cycle of reduced activity and increased dependency (11-13). Various health conditions appear to mediate the link between BMI and falls; conditions such as stroke or arthritis directly contribute to fall risks due to physical decline (39-41). Additionally, the use of medications associated with these health conditions, known as polypharmacy, has emerged as an independent risk factor for falls (6, 58).

Depression emerges as a significant mediator of injurious falls (50, 51), with depressive symptoms linked to accidental falls through cognitive and physiological mechanisms like impaired executive function (56). In some cases, depression can result from a severe fall leading to fracture or disability, further exacerbating fall-related fears, restricting activity, and perpetuating depressive symptoms (7, 36). Falls are known to have substantial social and psychological consequences, often leading to diminished self-confidence and subsequent restrictions in physical activity (3, 51-54).

Furthermore, obesity is associated with lower levels of physical activity, impaired cardiorespiratory fitness, and diminished knee muscle strength compared to lean individuals (15, 16). These factors potentially hinder obese individuals' ability to effectively correct changes in their body's center of mass and thereby prevent falls (21-25).

The age restriction for this review was set at 80 years old, underscoring that obese individuals over this age may need to prioritize goals other than weight reduction to mitigate fall risks (32). Existing observational studies suggest that weight loss in older adults may not consistently lead to improved health outcomes; sporadic weight loss could instead signal underlying health issues rather than improved diet or exercise habits (5, 15, 35). Obesity in older adults is linked with multiple comorbidities and physical limitations, although interventions focusing on weight loss and increased physical activity have shown potential to enhance physical function (18). However, the safety and effectiveness of weight loss therapies in older adults warrant further investigation.

Several limitations were identified in this review. Variations in sample sizes and gender distribution across studies hindered the generalization of findings, with single-gender studies particularly challenging due to health-related recruitment issues in certain populations (3, 31, 53, 54). Studies conducted using force platforms employed diverse measurement techniques and variables, precluding a standardized assessment of base of support (43, 46, 51, 54). Additionally, the lack of objective measurement of muscular strength variables in reviewed studies precluded specific analysis in this regard (3, 31). While BMI served as the primary factor influencing balance, the lack of uniformity in measurement units across different assessment methods limited comparability between studies.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, body mass index (BMI) significantly influences balance, predisposing individuals to an increased risk of falls, potential injurious falls, fear of falling, and limitations in physical activity and daily functioning. This impact extends beyond static balance, affecting dynamic balance as well. Falls among obese individuals can lead to severe consequences such as disability, hospitalization, and long-term care facility admissions. Psychologically, obesity correlates with feelings of incapacity and an increased risk of depression, which further exacerbates fall risks.

Future research should focus on understanding the mechanisms of fall recovery to better interpret fall risks among aging populations. Identifying high-risk populations is crucial for targeted interventions and prevention strategies to mitigate the impact of falls associated with obesity. Efforts in these areas are essential to enhance the quality of life and reduce the burden of fall-related injuries in vulnerable populations.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that we have read and understood the conflict of interest policies of the Journal of Growing Health.

We confirm that we have no financial, personal, or professional conflicts of interest that could influence the results, interpretations, or conclusions presented in the article.

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